

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 4(2025)

Investigating The Antioxidant Potential Of Brinjal Peel Extract On Edible Oil

Rimsha Maqbool¹, Bilal Haider², Rabia Hussain³, Aqsa Javaid⁴, Rabia Kanwal⁵, Dr Muhammad Abrar⁶, Arish Hayat⁷, Qaiser Ali Sultan⁸

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Rimsha Maqbool

University Of Agriculture Faisalabad,
Department Of Food Science And Technology
rimshamaqbool708@gmail.com

Bilal Haider

University Of Agriculture Faisalabad,
Department Food Science And Technology,
bilalmicrosoft123@gmail.com

Rabia Hussain

Government College University Faisalabad,
Department Food Science and Technology
rabiahussain017@gmail.com

Aqsa Javaid

University Institute of Food Sciences and
Technology, The University of Lahore, Lahore,
Pakistan
Email: aqsa.javed@uifst.uol.edu.pk

Rabia Kanwal

Post-Harvest research Centre, Ayub Agriculture
Research Institute, Jhang road, Faisalabad
Email: rabia018y@gmail.com

Dr Muhammad Abrar

Ayub Agricultural Research Institute
Faisalabad, Post-Harvest Research Centre
AARI Faisalabad
Email: mabrarft@gmail.com

Arish Hayat

Department Of Food Science And Technology,
Bzu, Multan
arishh93@gmail.com

Qaiser Ali Sultan

Pakistan Standards and Quality Control
Authority, Peshawar, KPK, Pakistan
ORCID 0000-0001-6479-176X
nakhuda@aup.edu.pk
nakhudasolo@gmail.com

Oxidation of lipids is a major problem of fats and oils in terms of economy and health. The proximate composition of Brinjal peel powder was as follows: moisture 92.17%, ash 7.86%, fat 2.47%, fiber 35.3%, protein 13.3%, and NFE 41.22%. DPPH and TPC were used to assess the antioxidant capacity of eggplant peel extract. The DPPH and TPC of eggplant peel extract were respectively (95.35% inhibition) and (87.55mg GAE/100g). Physicochemical analysis of eggplant peel extract was done which have findings for free fatty acids (0.85%), iodine value (142.42g 12/100 g), peroxide value (4.72meqO₂/kg oil), saponification value (188.89 mg KOH/g of oil), specific gravity (0.910g/cm³) and fatty acid profile C18:2 linoleic acid (70.01%). Different concentrations of extract up to 700 ppm, 1400 ppm, 2100 ppm, 2800ppm, 3500ppm, and 200 ppm, synthetic antioxidant were added to edible oil to prepare the oil blends. After 0th, 15th, 30th, 45th, and 60th day of storage period, physicochemical analysis for free fatty acids, iodine value, peroxide value, saponification value, specific gravity and antioxidant potential (DPPH, TPC) were performed. For free fatty acids after 60 days of storage, T₀ exhibited the highest value (0.96%), while T₅ had the lowest value (0.66%) and synthetic antioxidant had (0.77%). The iodine value indicated that T₀ had the greatest mean value (107.50 g [2/100g), whereas T_s had the lowest mean value (97.64 g 12/100g). T₀ exhibited the greatest rise in peroxide value (46.2 meq O₂/kg), whereas T₅ showed the least (6.85 meq O₂/kg) and T₆ had (13.89). T₀ had the greatest saponification value (171 mg KOH/g), whereas T₅ had the lowest value (166 mg KOH/g). T₀, (0.925) had the highest specific gravity rise. According to the fatty acid profile, saturated fatty acids increased while unsaturated fatty acids decreased after storage. T₅, scored highest in the sensory evaluation. The obtained data were statistically analyzed to find the level of significance under the 2-way factorial and CRD design. According to the results of this study, eggplant peel extract might be utilized as an alternative to a synthetic antioxidant to stop lipid oxidation in fat.

INTRODUCTION:

Natural antioxidants that are mainly plant based show great potential for oxidative stability and also have beneficial effects on human health (Shahidi et al., 2010). Essential oils are utilized successfully as food preservatives due to their antibacterial and antioxidant properties. Essential oils have been used to preserve several types of food, including meat, dairy products, salad dressing, mayonnaise, bread, and baked goods. Some studies have shown that synthetic antioxidants can cause toxicity. Antioxidant capacity of fruit extracts mainly depends on the phenolic compounds which exist in them. Food processing industries produce thousands of tons of peel, pomace and pulps on annual basis, which are important source of bioactive components (Chattop Srivastava adhyay et al., 2020). The majority of waste materials produced by the food processing industries well as from home hold knobiness contain pools and trimmings of fruits and vegetables which can be used as nutraceuticals(Xiao et al., 2017).

Lipid peroxidation is the major cause of deterioration of oil. It affects the quality and also comes undesired changes. These changes lower the chance of acceptance by the consumers so the industries suffer from great loss. Exposure to light, heat, chain reaction and radiations produce free radicals that cause the autoxidation of polyunsaturated lipids (Habib et al., 2004). The phenomena of free radicals production by lipid oxidation is a part of our everyday life. The human digestive system can tackle only small amount of these radicals, once these peroxides are absorbed in the body they cannot be removed and give rise to various diseases (Trombino et al., 2021).

Stability of fats and oil is the most important factor that must be kept in mind while handling of fats and oils. Their stability can either be increased by using synthetic antioxidants However, it's been realized that synthetic antioxidants can be hazardous to health which may cause enlargement of liver, hormonal imbalance and can cause cancer. Therefore, scientists are more focused on using natural antioxidants. Many parts of plants like peels, leaves, fruits, seeds and oils contain natural antioxidants like tannins, coumarone, anthocyanins, flavonoids, shanthones and lignin (Fadda et al., 2022). The most preferred way to use natural antioxidants is from natural sources, other methods can be more expensive and may not be applied easily or they may need some special processing condition. It must be kept in mind that how difficult and expensive it is to remove enough oxygen from the food product that will not cause any oxidation process.

Phenolics consist of a wide group of highly concentrated antioxidants, concerned with total antioxidant activity. The presence of Phenolics in plants depends upon various aspects nudging from source, method of processing, storage conditions and cultivar (Echegaray et al., 2022). Antioxidants can be employed to prevent oxidation of protein and fat. They prevent the activity of free radicals in oil. Antioxidant capacity of natural sit oxidants that ate de planted chemical structure, arrangement and moreover, some functional foods can also be prepared by locorporatigue. Some scientists have discovered that food was so can be applied to extend the oxidative stability of vegetable oil or some of products. Bo, food items that are more easily oxidized can be protected by incorporating suntrap antioxidants. It has been reported that potato post extract can hood as nature antioxidant to protect vegetable oil from rancidity (Toppino et al., 2016).

Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.), also known as aubergine in Europe and Brinjal in South Asia, is a significant vegetable crop cultivated in various countries across the subtropics, tropics, and Mediterranean regions. Its cultivars exhibit a wide diversity of fruit shapes, sizes, and colors. The high fiber contents and a low carbohydrate content observed in these vegetables also make its consumption useful in managing Diabetes mellitus (Taher et al., 2017). From nutritional point of view, eggplant has a very low energy value with low GI and is bland among the healthiest vegetable for its rich nutritional value including insoluble dietary fiber, vitamins, minerals and bioactive compounds (Sultana et al., 2012).

The bioactive properties of eggplant are mostly associated with high content in phenolic compounds, flavonoids and anthocyanins. Both anthocyanins and phenolic acids and have multiple properties beneficial for human health (Braga et al., 2016). Furthermore, phenolic acids of eggplant are highly present in the both peel and the pulp (Jung et al., 2011). Eggplant cultivars with dark purple skin receive considerably more attention for being much richer in anthocyanins, with much higher concentrations as compared to grapes

(Ansari and Singh et al., 2014).

The polyphenolics found in eggplant peels, particularly the anthocyanins, have a high level of antioxidant activity, which suggests that eggplant peels could be a natural, potent, and safe source of antioxidants. The limited use of anthocyanins in edible products was caused by their hydrophilic nature, which made them insoluble in the lipid phase; additionally, their high susceptibility to oxidative degradation loss of antioxidant activity at high temperatures and impartment of taste, odour, and colour (Horincar et al., 2019). Since numerous years, the extraction of oil from oil bearing plant material (oil seed) has been an important to industry. There are distinct sources of oil production that usage as for food, primal material in chemical products as well as lubricant. First thing that under concern is that the extraction of maximum oil from oleaginous material pursued to purification or refining of extracted raw oil. The storage condition of harvested material and pretreatment conditions are important in order to attain high quality of the oils. During the process of extraction of oil from oil seed significantly adopted by the most effective extraction method to optimize maximum oil as well as sustainment good quality of the oil (Condurache et al., 2019).

The techniques for extraction of oil has developed from simple manual pressing to sophisticated continuous processing technique in the modern days. The amelioration was required to enhance oil yield, valuable residues after extraction of oil and its quality amended. One of the crucial processing steps for the purification, identification or isolation of valuable compound from plant-based material is that "extraction" (Batabyal et al., 2017). Major problem for oil industry is lipid oxidation because in the process of processing and storage edible oil becomes more prone to photo oxidation and autoxidation. In autoxidation peroxide is the main product that produce objectionable flavor in products (Javani-Seraji et al., 2023).

Atherosclerosis, cancer, inflammation, accelerated ageing, and cardiovascular disease are just a few of the degenerative disorders that are brought on by the harmful free radical molecules that are created during lipid oxidation (Muhammad Awais et al., 2018). Antioxidants can be used to reduce these free radicals' detrimental effects. These antioxidants have a beneficial effect on human health by preventing cellular deterioration, which in turn reduces oxidative stress (Choe et al., 2010). In the food industry, synthetic antioxidants are frequently employed to prevent oxidative rancidity, which degrades nutritional value and quality attributes while also producing rancid flavor in food. When artificial antioxidants such butylated hydroxyl toluene (BHT) andbutylated hydroxyl anisole (BHA) react with the peroxide molecules found in food, they can cause carcinogenesis and damage to DNA, which can have detrimental effects on health. Because of this, using sources of low-cost, naturally occurring antioxidants, like agricultural byproducts as sources of bioactive chemicals, is a feasible strategy (Jung Eunju et al., 2011).

The use of naturally occurring fruit wastes to enhance human health has received more attention (Nwanna et al., 2019). A significant quantity of waste is generated during the manufacturing of several food products, including wines, plant-based oils, jams, jellies, and nectars. These waste products are an excellent source of carotenoid colors, polyphenols, phenolic acids, vitamin E, and vitamin C (ascorbic acid), and they are also rich in bioactive chemicals. Fruit waste materials such as husk, peels, and seeds are abundant in polyphenols (N.P et al., 2019). Particularly compared to other eggplant parts (pulp, leaf, stem, and calyx), eggplant peel contains the highest anthocyanin and polyphenol content and the strongest antioxidant activity (Gonzalez et al., 2011).

The polyphenolics found in eggplant peels, particularly the anthocyanins, have a high level of antioxidant activity, which suggests that eggplant peels could be a natural, potent, and safe source of antioxidants. The limited use of anthocyanins in edible products was caused by their hydrophilic nature, which made them insoluble in the lipid phase; additionally, their high susceptibility to oxidative degradation loss of antioxidant activity at high temperatures and impartment of color, odor, and taste. As a natural source of antioxidants, this study aims to show the antioxidant potential of aborigine peel extract and evaluate its effect on sunflower oil stability throughout a range of storage times. The antioxidant activity of Eggplant peel extract was also examined in this work using the total phenolic compound (TPC) and DPPH radical scavenging method (Kehili et al., 2018).

METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Sample

To get rid of the debris, dust, and foreign objects stuck to the surface, the eggplants cleaned. The peels will be clean and then dried at 55 °C in a hot air oven. Using a tiny laboratory grinding machine the dried material was ground into a fine powder. The powder was refined further by passing it through sieves with a mesh size of 80. Following processing, the powder then put in sealed plastic jars to be examined further at room temperature.

Proximate Analysis of Eggplant Peel Powder

Proximate analysis of Eggplant peel powder includes moisture, ash, fat, protein, fiber and carbohydrates will be performed.

Moisture

The moisture analysis was performed such as first of all about 10g of the sample was weighted and put in the moisture dish then place the sample in the hot air oven and heat it at the temperature of about 130 °C in the hot air oven for 1 to 2 hour. Then the sample was cooled at the room temperature and then weight the remaining sample. Then the weight of the sample before and after heating in the hot air oven was calculate to determine the moisture content. The reduction in the weight denotes the content of moisture. The content of moisture also shows the storability of powder. If moisture content is high then insect bacteria and mold can attract towards the seed and spoil them on storage. Moisture content in the sample was calculated by the given formula:

Moisture (%) = $\frac{\text{Weight of original moisture of sample (g)} - \text{Weight of dried sample (g)}}{\text{Weight of the original sample (g)}} \times 100$

Ash

First of all 10g of the sample was taken in the dry clean crucible and weight the sample. When the sample was incinerated then the moisture comes out and the organic material such as protein, oil and starch burn and ash was left behind. The sample was placed in the muffle furnace at the temperature of about 585°C overnight. Then the remaining material was cooled at room temperature by placing it at room temperature. The ash (residue) was consist of inorganic minerals that was non-combustible. The content of ash was calculated as a % of initial weight of the sample. The ash content indicates the overall content of minerals present in the sample. The content of ash was also consider as quality parameter such as it can affect the color of the product either high or low ash content require for the product. The content of ash in eggplant peel powder was calculated by the following formula:

Ash (%) = $\frac{\text{Ash sample weight (g)}}{\text{Weight of the sample (g)}} \times 100$

Crude Protein

The sample of eggplant peel powder or ground sample was taken approximately (0.15g to 0.2g) and weight the sample and place the sample into CAN (combustible nitrogen analyzer) protein analyzer. This process was fully automated process and this was begin by placing the sample into a hot oven where the sample was fully burned at the temperature of about (952°C). Then content of nitrogen gas comes out was measured and the mathematical formula was applied to determine the protein content in the sample. Low protein content indicate that it is use to make tender and crispy products like cakes and snacks etc. High content of protein shows that it is essential to make such foods that have chewy texture. The content of protein was determine as the percent of the sample weight. The low content of protein was desirable to make chewy texture, snack and cake like products as well as if the protein content was high the it was require to maintain maximum stability of the product.

Nitrogen (%) = Titer of 0.1N H₂SO₄, used x 0.0014 x 250 x 100

Weight of the sample x Volume of sample

Protein (%) = % N x 6.25

Crude Fat

Fat content in eggplant peel was determined by means of the method suggested in AOAC (2017). First of all 10g sample of eggplant peel powder was dried in the hot air oven. Then properly weigh the solvent extraction thimble (filter paper). Then place the sample into filter paper and again weight the thimble with the sample. After that dry the Soxhlet extraction flask and extraction of Crude Fat was performed by using hexane condensing 5 to 6 drops per second in Soxhlet extraction unit. Hence, 4 to 5 washings were done and for each washing 30 to 40 minutes were required and after extraction the hexane was evaporated in extraction flask in a rotatory evaporator and hot bath. When no odor was retained then dry the flask at 100 °C for 30 minutes in the hot air oven. The flask was cooled in the desiccator and weighed properly. Then the weight of the Crude Fat of eggplant peel powder was determined by the following formula:

Crude Fat (%) = Weight of hexane extract/ residue x 100

Sample weight

Crude Fiber

First of all 5g of dry peel powder was taken in the round bottom flask. Then pour 100ml of 1.25% H₂SO₄ into a round bottom flask and boil it at the Soxhlet unit for approximately 30 minutes. Then filter it with the linen cloth to collect the residue. Then these residues were put in the round bottom flask. Then pour approximately 100ml of 1.25% NaOH into the round bottom flask. Then weigh the crucible on the weighing balance then again dried the residue in hot air oven and calculate the weight of the sample. Then again charring of the sample was performed and the sample was placed in the muffle furnace for the purpose of ashing at the temperature of about 550°C. After ashing the sample was weighed again and the percentage of fiber was estimated through the following formula:

Crude fiber (%) = $\frac{\text{Residue weight} - \text{Weight after ashing}}{\text{Weight of the sample (g)}} \times 100$

Nitrogen Free Extract

NFE of eggplant peel powder was estimated by using the methodology suggested in AOAC (2017). The NFE of eggplant peel powder was calculated by the following formula:

Carbohydrates (%) = 100 - [Moisture (%) + Ash (%) + Protein (%) + Fat (%)]

Extraction of Eggplant peel

Sample Preparation

After drying, peel was ground into a fine powder, it was passed through 80 mesh sieves for further refining and kept at room temperature in an airtight container. Oil was extracted by using Soxhlet apparatus. After extraction, it will be filtered through filter paper to remove coarse particles. Firstly, constructed thimble with 15g sample. Then put them in the round bottom flask of the Soxhlet apparatus, add 250-300ml of n-hexane. In the extraction chamber of the Soxhlet apparatus, 3-4 thimbles containing 15g of sample each were put. When the heat source was turned on, the solvent began to boil or vaporize. These vapours were condensed into droplets when they come into contact with the cold-water circulation assembly. These drops landed on the sample, dissolving the oil. The cycle was repeated until all of the oil from the sample was removed. The solvent with oil was collected after 7-8 washings. The solvent was evaporated to obtain oil.

Physicochemical Analysis of Eggplant peel extract

Saponification value

First of all, diluted sample of the eggplant peel extract is subjected to filter paper and allowed to separate the scum, moisture as well as other trace elements present. After they have been confirmed to be dry to the bone they are graded based on a number 2.0 g of oil sample was accurately taken and transferred quantitatively into a 250ml Erlenmeyer flask. After this the 25ml of alcoholic potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution was slowly pipetted into the sample and the mixture well shaken. The above mixture was added in water bath and was refluxed for about 30 minutes while being occasionally shaken. Then, 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were also used. This sample was then titrated with 0.1N hydrochloric acid (HCl) up to a point that the pink colour disappeared and this took approximately one hour upon boiling. The saponification value of eggplant peel extract was calculated by the given formula:

$$\text{Saponification value (mg/g)} = \frac{56.1(B-S) \times N \text{ of HCL}}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Free fatty acids

The A 10 ml sample of eggplant peel extract was placed in a conical flask, and 25 ml of 95% ethanol was added. The mixture was stirred well until the oil was fully dissolved in the ethanol. Next, 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein were added, and the mixture was shaken forcefully. The mixture was then titrated with 0.1N NaOH, with continuous stirring, until a pink color was attained. The free fatty acid (FFA) value of eggplant peel extract was intended by the following formula:

$$\text{FFA (\%)} = \frac{\text{Alkali used (ml)} \times N \times 28.2}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}$$

Peroxide value

First, 5 ml of eggplant peel extract was placed into a 250 ml conical flask. Then, 30 ml of an acetic acid-chloroform solvent mixture (3:2) was mixed and stirred for about one minute until dissolved. Subsequently, ranging from 0 to 5 ml of standard KI solution was pipetted using Mohr pipette. The mixture was left to stand in a cool, dark place. Afterward, the sample solution was titrated with 0.1N sodium thiosulfate (Na_2SO_3), continuously stirring until the mixture turned yellow. Finally, a starch solution was employed as an indicator, with continuous shaking until the blue color disappeared. The peroxide value (PV) was determined using the following formula:

$$\text{PV (meq/kg)} = \frac{(B-S) \times N \times 1000 \times 100}{\text{Weight of oil (g)}}$$

Specific Gravity

To begin with, the pycnometer was saturated with acetone and evacuated to remove air then it was dried. Next, the pycnometer was weighed filled with the sample oil without any air bubble when removing the cap at the side arm. It was then taken out, the stopper was put on as tight as possible and the pycnometer immersed in a water bath for 30 minutes. Gently, any resent oil which may have leaked from the capillary opening was removed with the help of a tissue. Next, to check how clean the pycnometer was, the cap of the side arm was opened and the pycnometer was taken out of the water bath. The cap was then, removed from side arm; this was followed by the weighing of the sample at a temperature of 30 °C. The specific gravity of the eggplant peel extract was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Specific gravity} = \frac{\text{Oil sample weigh (g)} - C - A}{\text{Weight of the water (g)} - B - A}$$

Iodine value

Initially, 5 ml of the extracted solution from the eggplant peel was pipetted into an Erlenmeyer flask. Subsequently, 25 ml of (CCl_4) solution was added, and the mixture was stirred. Following this, Wij's solution was introduced, and the mixture was stirred vigorously once more. The solution was left to settle

for about 30 minutes in a well –indicated area where there was no direct contact with light. Distillation was carried out using a 10% potassium iodide solution, and 2 ml of the distilled solution was utilized. The volume of the solution in the flask was completed to the mark by distilled water and the contents of the flask were titrated against 0.

Fatty acid profile by GC-FID

The fatty acids composition of the raw peel extract of eggplant was done using chromatography with methods similar to what was explained by Ketenoglu (2020). To start with, separation of the oil and water layers was followed by transesterification of the oil to obtain the FAME. Vortexed 100 µl of eggplant peel extract with 5 ml of heptane and approximately 250 µl of sodium methoxide was added to it. The vortexing continued until three distinct layers formed: First of all, it is the top layer formed by the methyl esters, the second layer with impurities, and the third layer with the foam. The upper layer was the methyl esters; about 10µL was taken with a micro-syringe and placed into a vial for GC. Trans-esterification was done using boron trifluoride methanol complex (concentration 20% (w/w) BF₃ in methanol). For this process, 20 mg of the oil sample and 1 g/L of pentadecanoic acid (C₁₅:10 µl of concentrated HCl (0.007 mol, 0.007 g, ~0 ml of 4 N HCl) was added to approximate 0.005 g of CH₃OH (0.017 mol) in a 30 ml screw-cap test tube. The mixture was dried under nitrogen (N₂) and then re yellow dissolved in 6 ml of 0.5M methanolic NaOH solution. Once the tube is sealed, it was placed in the heating block at 80 °C and stirred for 30 mins. After that, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature and further 6 mL of BF₃-methanol complex has been added followed by the stirring at 80°C for 15 minutes. The sample was then cooled and 10 ml of water and 10 ml heptane were added, vortex for 1-2 min and prepared in aliquots for GC-FID analysis. GC-FID analysis was performed on the Shimadzu GC-17 with the FID and a DB WEX 30M 0.25 mM column prepared at the central HI-TECH Laboratory. The temperature program adopted in the separation of methyl esters of fatty acids was: starting temperature of 140°C held for 5 minutes and a further 30 minutes at 240°C with a rate of 4°C per minute. Injector and detector temperatures were 250±2°C and 260±2°C, respectively; Nitrogen (N₂) was used as carrier gas at 30±0.5 ml/min. Fatty acid concentrations were expressed as percentage via transesterification and analysis on both the oil samples.

DPPH assay

The antioxidant activity of the extracts was appraised using the 2,2 -diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging technique. Performing the assay requires 1 ml of methanol solution containing 0.1 mM DPPH and 3 ml of the sample and these were to be mixed vigorously. Such dark micro cuvettes were next incubated for 30 minutes (in the dark) to measure absorbance at wavelength 517nm. Therefore, 3 mL of ethanol for the ethanol sample. BHT is a butylated hydroxytoluene standard oxidant at an equivalent dose for the treatment of the control group.

Total phenolic content

Dissolve gallic acid 25mg to 25ml of distilled water to prepare a gallic acid stock solution. Prepare succession solutions with the ability to conduct up to 450 µg/ml dimensions-wise from the stock solution. The total phenolic content (TPC) test was done by transferring 125 µl of the sample to a test tube and gently mixing it with 500 µl of distilled water. Next, 6 minutes allowed for the addition of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, which was 125 µl. Following this, 1.25 ml of 7% sodium carbonate solution was added to the solution. The volume was then tuned to 3 ml with water, and the reaction was let to run for 90 mins. Absorbance readings of both the standard as well as the sample were made with the use of a UV-visible spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 760 nm.

P-Anisidine value

term “p-anisidine value” probably stands for the “p-Anisidine value”, which is a quantitative indicator that is utilized in the food industry and is most commonly associated with fats and oils. The Permalink Anisidine value (AV) measures the degree of unsaturation as well as the extent of oxidation products, particularly aldehydes which are associated with rancidity and objectionable flavours. Make sure that the oil or fat sample dissolves in isooctane to create a clear solution. Normally, a 1% (w/v) solution is obtained by weighing 1 gm of the sample and dissolving it in 100 ml of isooctane. Transfer 5 milliliters of the isooctane to a test tube or cuvette that has been appropriately cleaned. Record the absorbance of this solution at wavelength of 350 nm using a spectrophotometer. This serves as the blank (A blank). Transfer 5 milliliters of the sample solution into another test tube or cuvette. Finally, you need to add 1 milliliter of the p-Anisidine reagent on top of the sample solution. Stir the solution gently and let it stand for approximately 10 minutes at room temperature. Dilute the resulting solution to a final volume of 1 ml and use a spectrophotometer to read the absorbance at 350 nm.

Addition of Eggplant peel extract in sunflower oil

Different amounts of Brinjal peel extract will be added to 100 milliliters of vegetable oil to act as a natural antioxidant. In accordance with the treatment plan, 100 ml of sunflower oil will be supplemented with Brinjal (eggplant) peel extract. The identical conditions will also apply to a control sample of sunflower oil T₀ that does not include antioxidants. The oil samples from each treatment will be taken out every 15 days to assess the antioxidant activity of the Brinjal (Eggplant) peel extract. 200 ppm of synthetic antioxidant BHT will be employed in the T₆ therapy.

Table 1: Treatment plan for application of Brinjal (Eggplant) peel extract in sunflower oil

Treatment	Vegetable oil (ml)	Eggplant peel extract (ppm)	Synthetic Antioxidant BHT(ppm)
T ₀	100	---	---
T ₁	100	700	---
T ₂	100	1400	---
T ₃	100	2100	---
T ₄	100	2800	---
T ₅	100	3500	---
T ₆	100		200

Analysis of Sunflower oil during Storage Study

The prepared samples were stored at 25°C for investigation of quality characteristics and anti-oxidative stability at intervals of 0, 15, 30, 45, and 60 days.

Physicochemical analysis of sunflower oil

Saponification value

The sample was taken and then all the impurities like moisture scum and trace elements was removed with the help of filter paper. It was confirmed that oil sample was fully dry then weight 2.0g of oil sample. The sample of oil was taken into the Erlenmeyer flask of 250ml. Then oil sample was completely mixed with the (KOH) solution. The alcoholic potassium hydroxide (KOH) content that was used to determine the saponification value was about 25ml and it was pipette slowly into the oil blend sample. Then this sample was reflux in water bath for about 30 minutes. Sample was shake vigorously followed by addition of about 2-3 drops of Phenolphthalein indicator. Than it is treated with the 0.5N of HCL until the pink color changes to the clear solution this clarity was achieved within one hour of boiling. Blank determination was also

measured along with sample determination.

Free fatty acids

The level of free fatty acids in the oil blend was determined on the basis of the standard procedure described in Wellington and Neuza (2021). A sample of about 10ml oil blend was added in a conical flask then 25ml ethanol was poured in and it was swirled until the oil sample was homogenous in ethanol. Then 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added followed by vigorous shaking and 0. The mixture was then titrated using 1N NaOH while stirring until the pink color persisted. FFA value of oil blend was calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{FFA (\%)} = \frac{\text{Alkali used (ml)} \times \text{N} \times 28.2}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}$$

Peroxide value

Oil blend peroxide value was calculated according to the standard method suggested in Amna et al. (2022). First of all 5ml of oil blend sample was taken into a 250ml of conical flask. Subsequently the precipitation was dissolved with 30ml of acetic acid-chloroform (3:2) solvent mixture by whirling for about 1 minute. Subsequently, 0-5ml of standard (KI) solution was pipette using mohr slanting pipette. This mixture was allowed to stand in a cool and dark area. After that, dilute the sample solution with a quotient of 0. Sodium thiosulphate solution in Na₂SO₃. Continuously stir the solution until the yellow color of the mixture was appeared. Subsequently, the solution of starch was used as an indicator, vigorously shaking require until the turned blue color vanished. The peroxide value was calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{PV (meq/kg)} = \frac{(\text{B-S}) \times \text{N} \times 1000 \times 100}{\text{Weight of oil (g)}}$$

Specific Gravity

First of all, take some time to make sure that the pycnometer is as dry as possible. Then it was filled with the oil sample in such a manner that it did not get in contact with the air bubbles once the side arm cap is removed. The stopper was injected and the pycnometer was positioned into the water bath for 30 minutes then carefully the remaining oil was wiped off that came out from the opening of the capillary. The bulb of the pycnometer was clean and devoid of moisture and the side arm was unscrewed to remove it from the water bath. The cap was take off from the side arm and immediately weigh the sample accurately, it was ensured that temperature should be 30 °C at the time of Specific gravity of eggplant peel extractl was computed by the following formula:

$$\text{Specific gravity} = \frac{\text{Weight of oil sample (g)}}{\text{Water weight (g)}} = \frac{\text{C-A}}{\text{B-A}}$$

Iodine value

5ml of sample was pipette into the Erlenmeyer flask, then 25ml of carbon tetrachloride (CCL) solution as well as continuously stirred the sample before Wij,s solution was added. The content of all the sections should be evenly distributed. Then the solution was allowed to stand for about 30mints in a location devoid of light. This distillation was achieved by adding 2ml of distilled solution that contained 10% of potassium iodide solution. Then the flask contents were titrating against 0.1N of sodium thionphate and starch solution was applied as an indicator in this phenomenon. A bank reading was also conducted in such a manner and the given formula was applied to calculate.

$$\text{Iodine value} = \frac{(\text{B-S}) \times \text{N} \times 12.69}{\text{Weight of the sample}}$$

Fatty acid profile by GC-FID

First of all the fatty acid methyl esters were produced from the oil through the process called transesterification. The 100 µl of oil blend was vortex within the 5ml of heptane after that, about 250 NaOMe was added in the current mixture. That mixture was then vortexed until there were three distinct layers. This means that epical layer was comprises of methyl ester. Hence, the second and third layers were consisting of impurities and foam respectively. The upper layer was collected in important role with the help of micro-syringe and this viald sample was prosecuted for GC analysis. The process of transesterification used the boron trifluoride methanol complex (20% BF₃ in methanol). Utilizing BF₃-methanol to change fatty acids into their methyl ester equivalents is one of the easiest and most rapid methods. A 30ml screw-cap test tube containing 1gL of pentadecanoic acid (C_{15:0}) n-methanol was filled with 20mg of an oil sample as an internal reference. The mixture was dried using nitrogen (N₂), and the residue was then dissolved in 6ml of a 0.5M methanolic NaOH solution. The tube was sealed with a cap and warmed to 80 °C while being stirred for about 30 minutes. BF₃-methanol solution in the amount of 6 ml was added to the sample once the tube had reached room temperature. The material was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 80 °C for 15 minutes. The samples were brought back to room temperature before being mixed with 10 ml of water and 10 ml of heptane for 10 minutes using a magnetic stirrer and vortexed for 1-2 minutes. Then, in aliquots in an auto sampler, the methylation samples were examined using GC-FID. The GC-FID analysis was completed in the "Central HI-TECH Laboratory" with the aid of a (GC-17 SHIMADZU) gas chromatograph outfitted with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a DB WEX 30M 0.25 mm column. The following temperature programs were used to separate the methyl esters of fatty acids: 5 minutes at 140°C and 30 minutes at 240°C at a 4minute rate. A 2µl sample volume was administered. A temperature was selected for the injector. The injector temperature was set to 250°C, while the detector temperature was set at 260°C. At a flow rate of 30m/min, the carrier gas was nitrogen (N₂). The concentration of fatty acids was represented as a percentage. Both oil samples underwent transesterification and analysis.

DPPH assay

First of all, completely mix the 1ml of methanol (MeOH) of 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) with approximately 1ml of oil blend sample. The oil sample was subsequently mix and allow to stand in the cool and dark place for approximately 30 minutes at ambient temperature. The absorbance of the solution was then investigating against 517nm blank reagent. The antioxidant activity was calculated as the percentage of inhibition DPPH radical and predicted by the following formula:

Reduction of absorbance % = $\frac{AB-AA}{AA} \times 100$

AA

Total phenolic content

The calibration curve was formed by using 5ml Folin Ciocalteu reagent and 4ml sodium carbonate solution (75g/L). The mixture was kept at incubation for 30 minutes at room temperature. Absorbance was checked at wavelength of 765nm at 20C. Then 1ml of eggplant peel extract was mixed with above mentioned reagents and after 30 minutes' absorbance was checked.

Frying stability analysis

French fries were prepared to check the frying stability of sunflower oil bland by following Fan et al. (2013).

Sensory evaluation

The 9-point Hedonic Score System was used to assess the consumer acceptance of French Ines for color, aroma, taste, texture, chewing, and overall acceptability, as reported try Meilgaard et al (2007). Faculty

members and postgraduate students from NIFSAT participated in the evaluation to choose the best treatment oil blend for French fries. The scale ranged from 1, termed as extremely disliked, to 9, termed as extremely liked. The fries were put in random boxes and presented in front of an evaluation panel for an unbiased opinion. The water was provided to the panelists to enhance the result's accuracy 34.

Storage Stability

The storage stability study was measured at different storage time. The samples were filled in the separate plastic cups and stored at the room temperature for the investigation of quality attributes and anti-oxidative stability of the mayonnaise 0, 15th, 30th, 45th and 60th days of time intervals.

Statistical Analysis

The values obtained from the results of all parameters were then expressed as mean \pm SD. The data collected was then analyzed statistically with the help of one -way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Unlike treatment groups were dogged by applying the Tukey test at an implication altitude of 5% for statistical differences identification (Montgomery, 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moisture

The shelf life of a product is significantly affected by its moisture content, a high level of moisture in the product promotes the growth of microbes. It is determined for various reasons including legal and label requirements, commercial value, food quality, improved processing techniques, and considerations for storage stability. The mean value of moisture content was $92.17 \pm 4.59\%$. Lipids which include fats and oils are a crucial component of our diet. Fat is the most affordable energy source which affects the physical and sensory qualities of items. It serves as a transporter of the body for fat-soluble vitamins. Crude Fat content in powdered capsicum seeds, which was $2.47 \pm 0.04\%$.

Crude Protein

Proteins are collections of amino acid chains, and the quantity of each determines the quality of the sample. Nitrogen content is frequently used to calculate the presence of crude protein in a sample. Crude protein had a mean value of $13.3 \pm 0.66\%$. These results also comparable with the study of Velasco et al., who determined the oxidative stability of virgin olive oil

Crude Fiber

The insoluble portion of a food product left over following acid and alkaline by hdrolysis is referred to as crude fiber. The crude fiber includes real cellulose and insoluble lignin. A kind of carbohydrate, fiber is essential for good health. Dietary fiber is a crucial part of digestion because of its capacity to store water. Many fruit leftovers include fiber, which is employed in the production of other cuisines. Brinjal (eggplant) peel powder had $35.3 \pm 1.77\%$ crude fiber. Our results are also relate with the Silarova et al. (2019) who monitoring of chlorogenic acid and antioxidant capacity of *Solanum melongena* L. (eggplant) under different heat and storage treatments

Total Ash

The most prevalent minerals in ash include potassium, calcium, manganese, mercury, lead, and cadmium. Ash is a mixture of several different minerals. Despite not being a nutrient and, contains some minerals that are essential for the development and maintenance of good health. Ash had a mean value of 7.86% and a standard deviation of 0.39%. The findings wat comparable to those of Chouaibs et al. (2015), who identified the ingredients in Brinjal (eggplant) peel powder.

Nitrogen-Free Extract (NFE)

"NFE" typically stands for "Nitrogen-Free Extract." NFE represents the portion of a food or feed sample that is soluble in a solvent like ethanol and consists mainly of carbohydrates, sugars, starches, and some organic acids.

The proximate analysis of food or feed involves determining its major components, including moisture, protein, fat, fiber, ash, and NFE. These components provide valuable information about the nutritional composition and quality of the sample. NFE is often calculated by subtracting the percentages of moisture, protein, fat, fiber, and ash from 100%. The NFE, which represents the carbohydrate content, ranged from 31.9±2.06. The finding was comparable to those of Chouaibs et al. (2015), who identified the ingredients in Brinjal (eggplant) peel powder.

Table 2: Proximate composition (%) of eggplant peel powder

Analysis	Mean value
Moisture	9.17±0.46
Ash	7.86±0.39
Fiber	35.3±1.77
Protein	13.3±0.66
Fat	2.47±0.04
Nitrogen free extract	31.9±2.06

Antioxidant analysis of eggplant peel extract

DPPH radicle scavenging assay

The 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) is an efficient method for evaluating the antioxidant capability of eggplant peel extracts and specific bioactive substances. Free radical scavenging is estimated by using the DPPH radical, most often a proton radical. Free radicals were created as a result of the loss of hydrogen atoms from unsaturated fatty acids, which can accelerate the synthesis of lipids. While lipid oxidation is stopped by delaying the chain reactions, the oxidation process is initiated by scavenging free radicals. Table 4.2 showed the DPPH antioxidant activity of eggplant peel extract. DPPH inhibition of eggplant peel extract was 95.35±5.16 (% inhibition). Hamed et al (2019), who conducted a comparison research on eggplant peel extract validated the results of antioxidant activity. The results of this investigation revealed that the antioxidant activity of capsicum seed extract was 85.35%.

Total phenolic content

Numerous molecules containing polyphenol structures or phenol rings, such as phenolic alcohols and phenolic acids, are classified as phenolic compounds. In terms of polyphenols, flavonoids, and non-flavonoids are the two main classifications. As examples of non-flavonoids, benzoic acid and cinnamic acid can be used. Plant tissues contain several hydroxybenzoic and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives. The total phenolic contents (TPC) of eggplant peel extract are displayed in Table 4.2 eggplant peel extract had a mean and standard deviation of 87.55±3.15 mg GAE/100g.

Table 3. Antioxidant characteristics of eggplant peel extract

Analysis	Value
DPPH	95.35±5.16
TPC	87.55±3.15 mg GAE per 100g

Physicochemical analysis of eggplant peel extract

Free fatty acids

Triglycerides (TGs) of vegetable oil are digested to provide free fatty acids (CFAs). Their development mostly occurs during the handling, manufacturing, and storage of oil and the processing of raw materials. The amount of FFA in the oil was used to calculate how much the lipase action had damaged the oil's glycerides. The kind and quality of the raw material used, the environment in which it was gathered, the techniques used to produce and store the oil, the oil's age and level of deterioration, and many other factors all influence the FFA content of vegetable oil. The free fatty acid of Brinjal peel extract is displayed in Table 4.3 which has a mean value and standard deviation of 0.89±0.05.

Iodine value

The relative level of oil unsaturation as determined by halogen absorption is shown by the iodine value. The link between the degree of unsaturation and these two qualities allows one to predict the melting point and oxidative stability from the iodine value. iodine content directly correlates with increased unsaturation and decreased oxidative stability. These results are frequently expressed in terms of the amount of iodine absorbed per 100ml of oil. The iodine value of eggplant peel extract is displayed in Table 4.3 as a value, iodine value had a mean value and a standard deviation of 142.42±6.29(g 1/100g oil). These findings were comparable to those of Chouaibi et al (2015), who identified the iodine value in eggplant peel extract which was 143.42(g 1/100g oil).

Peroxide value

The quantity of primary oxidation products like peroxide and hydroperoxides created during the initial phases of oil and fat oxidation is measured by the peroxide value, which serves as an analysis for oil oxidative rancidity. Reactive oxygen content, measured in milliequivalents of free iodine per kg of fat, is known as the peroxide value. It is a major contributor to the degradation, off-flavoring, and toxin generation in oils. Despite having no flavor or odor of their own, hydro peroxides are unstable and decompose into compounds like aldehydes, which have a strong, unpleasant flavor and odor. The peroxide value is often used to assess the presence of these undesirable activities in oils and foods. Peroxide value had a mean value of 4.72±0.60(meqO₂/kg) and these findings were comparable to those of Issaoui M. et al. (2019), who identified the labeling and standardization of edible oils.

Table 4: Physicochemical attributes of eggplant peel extract

Component	Percentage
Free fatty acids	0.85±0.05
Peroxide value(meqO ₂ /kg oil)	4.72±0.60
Saponification value(mg KOH/g oil)	188.89±7.37

Iodine value (gI ₂ /100g oil)	142.42±6.29
Specific gravity (g/cm ³)	0.910±0.05

Fatty acid profile by GC-FID

Fatty acids (FAS) and other volatile compounds are often investigated using gas chromatography (Gc) and a flame ionization detector. Nutritional value of oil is largely impacted by the FAS composition in it. The fatty acid concentration of plant oils is highly influenced by a variety of elements, such as plant species, growth location, maturation stage, and environmental conditions. FAS are split into two groups based on the saturation level: saturated and unsaturated. The two primary subgroups of unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) are monounsaturated and polyunsaturated. Monounsaturated fatty acids only have double bond, in contrast to polyunsaturated fatty acids. The three most common UFAs are linoleic, oleic, and linolenic acids. Fatty acids in vegetable oils typically include one carboxyl group and so even number of carbon atom between 16 and 18. To determine the fatty acid content of the oils under investigation, the quantity of saturated and UFAs is used. Oil becomes increasingly oxidation-prone as its degree of unsaturation rises. Fatty acids (FAS) and other volatile compounds are often investigated using gas chromatography (Gc) and a flame ionization detector. The rational value of oil is largely impacted by the FAS composition in it. The fatty acid concentration of plant oils in highly influenced by a variety of elements, such as plant species, growth location, maturation stage, and environmental conditions. To determine the fury acid content of the oils under investigation, the quantity of saturated and unsaturated (UAFs) is used.

Table 5. Fatty acids profile of Brinjal peel extract

Fatty acid (%)	Concentration (%)
Solvent (methanol)	0.3
Heptacosane	09
Methyltriacontane	15
2-methyletritriacontane	10.5
Hexatriacontane	49
2-methylehexatriacontane	8.2
3-methylehexatriacentone	2.1
Octacosane	3.7
Nonacosane	2.4

Stabilization of sunflower oil with eggplant peel extract

Different quantities of eggplant peel extract (700ppm,1400ppm,2100ppm, 2800ppm, 3500ppm) and 200ppm synthetic antioxidant are added to sunflower oil and kept into room temperature. The oil mix samples were analyzed on the 0th, 15th, 30th, 45th, 60th day of storage. To assess the oxidative deterioration of oil over the storage period, various analysis was carried out. Those analyses and their results have been discussed under the following headings.

Free Fatty acid

Free fatty acids mainly define the cleanliness and the age of the oils in the market. The amount of FFAs depends on several parameters, such as enzyme activity, especially lipase activity, humidity, the type of fats and oils, extraction methods, and storage conditions and temperature. The presence of FFA in fats and oils can be associated with the fact that the higher their content, the higher the likelihood of their oxidation. It has been observed that oxidation is detrimental to color and flavor and causes rancidity in fats and oils. Hence there is need to always monitor the levels of unsaturated fats as an indication of rancidity for edible fats and oil products. In the presence of water, triglycerides undergo hydrolysis to produce FFA. These FFAs are used as an energy substrate for certain tissues and are adequate to supply an appropriate amount of ATP.

The days factor was also highly significant ($p < 0.01$), showing that free fatty acid content increased over time. Additionally, the interaction between treatment and days was significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that the rate of free fatty acid increase varied depending on the treatment. The data indicate that oils with higher concentrations of Brinjal peel extract (T_5) had the lowest free fatty acid content throughout the storage period, demonstrating the extract's effectiveness in inhibiting oxidation then the synthetic antioxidants (T_6) 200ppm.

These findings align with previous research by Kelly N.P et al. (2019), which demonstrated that strategies for enrichment and purification of polyphenols from fruit-based materials. This correlation underscores the potential of utilizing agricultural by-products, like Brinjal peel, to increase the shelf life and nutritional quality of food goods through natural antioxidant properties.

Table 6: Table of means of free fatty acids (%) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T_0	0.40±0.01	0.61±0.06	0.87±0.03	0.90±0.05	0.96±0.04	0.75 ^a
T_1	0.37±0.03	0.57±0.04	0.77±0.08	0.85±0.011	0.90±0.01	0.69 ^b
T_2	0.36±0.02	0.52±0.01	0.74±0.05	0.80±0.04	0.85±0.013	0.65 ^c
T_3	0.35±0.05	0.49±0.03	0.64±0.02	0.75±0.06	0.80±0.09	0.60 ^d
T_4	0.34±0.04	0.45±0.07	0.57±0.09	0.63±0.02	0.79±0.05	0.55 ^e
T_5	0.32±0.02	0.40±0.09	0.48±0.06	0.57±0.01	0.66±0.08	0.48 ^f
T_6	0.39±0.07	0.46±0.012	0.54±0.04	0.67±0.07	0.77±0.03	0.56 ^e
Mean	0.31 ^e	0.5 ^d	0.65 ^c	0.73 ^b	0.81 ^a	

Iodine value

The iodine value expresses the relative degree of unsaturation in oil as measured by halogen uptake. An estimate of melting point and oxidative stability can be derived from the iodine value due to the relationship between degree of unsaturation and these two properties. Unsaturation and lower oxidative stability increase in direct proportion to the iodine value. The findings are often reported in terms of the quantity of iodine that was absorbed for every 100 grams of oil or fat. The results are usually expressed as the amount of iodine absorbed per 100g of the oil or fat. During the 60 days of storage study iodine was

analyzed in sunflower oil samples at regular intervals. Table 4.9 shows the results of statistical analysis of variance regarding iodine number of all allocated oil samples at 0, 15, 30, 45, 60 days of storage. The outcomes revealed that iodine value of oil decreased with the increment of storing phase. On the other hand iodine value increase with the increase in eggplant peel extract in sunflower oil. Lowest iodine value on the 0th day was recorded for T₀ (111.37I₂g/100g) as it contain no antioxidant and T₆ having synthetic antioxidant had iodine value (121.40 I₂g/100g) and the iodine values observed in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅ were 112.37 I₂g/100g, 114.86 I₂g/100g, 116.39 I₂g/100g, 118.39 I₂g/100g and 120.40 I₂g/100g respectively showing a continuous increase from T₂ to T₅ with the more and more addition of natural antioxidants. The results of the study are also in accordance with the findings of the Javani-Seraji et al. (2023) who studied the influences of extraction techniques on the efficiency of pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) peel extracts in oxidative stability of edible oils.

Table 7: Table of means of Iodine value (gI₂/100g of oil) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	111.37±0.70	90.30±1.37	86.29±1.31	81.27±0.24	75.25±1.15	88.89 ^g
T ₁	112.37±1.71	92.31±1.41	85.28±2.30	82.27±1.25	79.26±0.21	90.29 ^f
T ₂	114.86±2.74	94.31±0.44	89.30±1.36	84.28±0.28	81.27±1.24	92.80 ^e
T ₃	116.39±3.77	97.32±1.48	91.30±1.39	87.29±1.33	80.27±2.22	94.51 ^d
T ₄	118.39±2.80	106.35±2.62	102.34±1.56	96.32±2.47	93.31±1.42	103.34 ^b
T ₅	120.40±1.83	115.38±1.78	105.35±3.60	101.34±1.54	98.33±3.50	108.16 ^a
T ₆	121.40±1.84	100.33±1.53	95.32±1.45	90.30±1.37	85.28±1.30	98.52 ^c
Mean	116.88 ^a	99.47 ^b	93.59 ^c	89.01 ^d	84.71 ^e	

Peroxide value

The peroxide value is an analysis used in evaluating oxidative rancidity since it involves determining the amount of primary oxidation products of the oils including peroxide and hydro peroxide in the initial stage of oil and fat oxidation. This value is defined from the amount of reactive oxygen in milli equivalents of free iodine per kilogram of fat. Peroxide value is also useful in determining off flavoring, deterioration, and toxin formation in the oils. Hydro peroxides by themselves may have no odor or taste but are not stable and break down into other compounds like aldehydes, which have an extremely foul odor and taste. In oils and fats, for example, the peroxide value is often employed to assess the magnitude of these undesirable reactions.

The interaction between treatment and days was significant (p < 0.05), suggesting that the rate of peroxide value increase varied with different treatments. Oils with Higher concentrations of Brinjal peel extract (T₅) existed the lowest peroxide values throughout the storage period, demonstrating the extract's effectiveness in inhibiting lipid peroxidation then the synthetic antioxidants (T₆) 200ppm.

These results are in agreement with the findings of Xu X et al. (2021) which showed that synthetic phenolic antioxidants: metabolism, hazards and mechanism of action. Phenolic content have inhibitory effect towards increasing peroxides value. Increase in peroxides value lower the stability. Antioxidant remains effective only for specific time and after that time they start to lose their activity. So natural

antioxidants should be used to prevent the activity loss so that oxidation may be reduced in sunflower oil and other oil containing product

Their study similarly observed that higher concentrations of natural antioxidants effectively slowed the increase in peroxide values, highlighting the potential of using natural sources like Brinjal peel extract to enhance the oxidative stability of edible oil.

Table 8: Table of means of Peroxide value (meq/kg oil) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	1.06±0.02	4.06±0.36	16.16±1.32	28.32±1.61	46.42±3.67	19.20 ^a
T ₁	1.05±0.03	2.82±0.22	7.97±0.63	15.97±1.27	31.97±2.54	11.95 ^b
T ₂	1.04±0.09	1.95±0.03	4.55±0.36	9.85±0.76	13.15±1.05	6.10 ^d
T ₃	1.03±0.08	1.79±0.04	3.16±0.08	4.94±0.39	8.34±0.66	3.85 ^e
T ₄	1.02±0.02	1.12±0.09	2.93±0.05	4.75±0.40	6.93±0.55	3.26 ^f
T ₅	1.01±0.04	1.06±0.08	2.85±0.23	4.25±0.36	6.85±0.54	3.20 ^f
T ₆	1.08±0.03	2.44±0.04	10.49±0.88	11.94±0.95	13.89±0.21	7.96 ^c
Mean	1.04 ^e	2.25 ^d	6.94 ^c	11.35 ^b	18.19 ^a	

Saponification value

Saponification value is the important variable that play significant role to provide information regarding stability of the oil. Saponification value indicates the presence of free fatty acids in the oil. Results further revealed that storage days also have highly significant impact on the saponification values of the sunflower oil. Combined effect of treatment and storage days had significant impact on the saponification values of the sunflower oil. Results of the study showed that there is significant impact among the mean values of all treatments. At 0th day, T₀ showed the highest saponification value (175mg KOH/g) as it contains no antioxidant and T₆ having synthetic antioxidant showed saponification value (171 mg KOH/g) and saponification values observed inT1, T2, T3, T4 and T5 were 170 mg KOH/g, 169 mg KOH/g, 168 mg KOH/g, 167 mg KOH/g, and 166mgKOH/g respectively showing a continuous decrease from T₁ to T₅ with the addition of natural antioxidants. However, storage study showed higher value at 60th day for T₀ (191mg KOH/g) and T₅ showed the lowest saponification value 186 mg KOH/g. Results further elaborated that with the increase in Brinjal peel extract percentage in the sunflower oil, saponification values decreased. On the other hand, with the increase in storage days, saponification values of the sunflower oil also increased.

The results of the study harmonized with Ali et al. (2015) who investigated the effect of Eucalyptus citriodora extract on stability vegetable oil blends. The saponification value increased in storage time of 100 days of both stabilized and non-stabilized oils. The results were also compared with the findings of the Kehili et al. (2018) who investigated the oxidative stability of the sunflower and olive oils after supplementation with tomato peels.

Table 9: Table of means of Saponification value (mg KOH/g) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	175±1.75	187±2.33	189±2.45	190±2.50	192±2.60	186 ^a
T ₁	190±1.86	175±1.75	180±1.00	185±1.25	190±1.86	180 ^{bc}
T ₂	169±2.45	174±2.70	179±2.95	184±2.20	189±2.38	179 ^{bcd}
T ₃	168±2.40	173±2.65	178±2.90	183±2.30	184±2.40	178 ^{bcd}
T ₄	167±1.35	172±1.60	177±1.85	182±1.34	186±1.35	177 ^{cd}
T ₅	166±1.33	171±1.87	176±1.80	181±1.05	187±1.33	176 ^d
T ₆	171±1.55	176±1.30	181±1.05	186±1.80	191±2.05	181 ^b
Mean	189.00 ^a	184.43 ^b	180.00 ^c	175.43 ^d	169.43 ^e	

Specific gravity

Specific gravity is the important variable that play decisive role to provide information regarding stability of the oil. Results further revealed that storage days also has non-significant impact on the specific gravity of the sunflower oil. Combined effect of treatment and storage days also revealed the non-significant impact on the specific gravity values of the sunflower oil. Results of the study showed that there is no significant impact among the mean values of all treatments. Results further elaborated that with the increase in pea pod extract percentage in the sunflower oil, specific gravity values increased. On the other hand, with the increase in storage days, specific gravity of the sunflower oil also increased. Lowest specific gravity on the 0th day was recorded for T₀ (0.911) and highest specific gravity on 0th day was recorded for T₅ (0.918) while T₁ (0.914), T₂ (0.914), T₃ (0.913), T₄ (0.912) and T₆ (0.916) showed specific gravity value respectively. At 60th day the highest value of specific gravity was seen at T₅ (0.932) and lowest value was of T₀ (0.923).

The results of the study also match with the findings of the Kehili et al. (2018) who investigated the oxidative stability of the sunflower and olive oils after supplementation with tomato peels.

Table 10: Table of means of Specific gravity (g/cm³) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	0.911±0.03	0.914±0.04	0.917±0.09	0.920±0.04	0.923±0.02	0.917
T ₁	0.914±0.06	0.918±0.08	0.921±0.03	0.924±0.08	0.927±0.03	0.920
T ₂	0.914±0.01	0.917±0.02	0.920±0.04	0.923±0.09	0.926±0.04	0.920
T ₃	0.913±0.05	0.916±0.05	0.919±0.01	0.922±0.07	0.925±0.06	0.919
T ₄	0.912±0.04	0.915±0.09	0.918±0.08	0.921±0.02	0.924±0.05	0.918

T₅	0.918±0.06	0.927±0.09	0.922±0.06	0.928±0.02	0.932±0.07	0.927
T₆	0.916±0.02	0.921±0.04	0.922±0.03	0.919±0.02	0.922±0.04	0.918
Mean	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.93	

Table 11: Table of means of p- Ansidine value of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T₀	3.11±0.18	3.78±0.10	3.99±0.17	4.78±0.14	4.96±0.15	4.12 ^a
T₁	3.09±0.17	3.54±0.13	3.96±0.16	4.54±0.19	4.78±0.20	3.98 ^b
T₂	3.07±0.15	3.48±0.01	3.83±0.3	4.43±0.5	4.65±0.9	3.89 ^{bc}
T₃	3.06±0.16	3.39±0.5	3.69±0.4	4.23±0.7	4.44±0.08	3.76 ^c
T₄	3.05±0.19	3.20±0.3	3.44±0.1	4.13±0.3	4.30±0.17	3.62 ^d
T₅	3.03±0.4	3.05±0.7	3.23±0.5	4.03±0.9	4.20±0.6	3.51 ^f
T₆	3.10±0.11	3.22±0.15	3.54±0.19	4.18±0.12	4.23±0.14	3.65 ^{ed}
Mean	3.07 ^c	3.38 ^e	3.67 ^d	4.33 ^b	4.51 ^a	

DPPH Assay

DPPH test is done to assess the anti-oxidant potential of any extract. It contains proton that act as free radical which have specific absorption property and when it interacts with other free radical scavenger it lowers down. DPPH free radical has hydrogen atom that make it a scavenger. DPPH has nitrogen radicals (not highly reactive) and transient peroxide radicals (basically involve in oxidation reaction).

DPPH free radical scavenging assay was used to check the antioxidant potential of Brinjal peel extract. Antioxidant potential of Brinjal peel extract increased as its concentration increases.

The interaction between treatment and storage time are significant. T₅ that had 3500ppm of Brinjal peel extract showed the high antioxidant potential throughout the storage time of 60 days. Results further elaborated that with the increase in eggplant peel extract percentage in sunflower oil, antioxidant activity increased. On the other hand with the increase in storage days, antioxidant activity of sunflower oil decreased. The results showed similarity with Nour et al. (2018) who studied tomato peel extract in refined sunflower, rapeseed and corn oil and storage study showed increasing trend in scavenging behavior of different oils.

The reason for impact of antioxidants on DPPH radical scavenging is that they have hydrogen-donating ability and DPPH is a stable free radical and accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable molecule Shabbir et al. (2015).

Table 12: Table of means of DPPH Assay (%) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	47.13±2.67	43.93±3.42	39.71±3.21	39.10±2.98	37.19±3.73	41.82 ^f
T ₁	53.83±2.78	50.63±2.65	46.41±2.41	43.67±3.45	40.93±3.31	46.73 ^e
T ₂	55.70±2.56	52.50±2.78	48.28±3.21	45.54±2.34	42.8±3.83	49.20 ^d
T ₃	59.33±2.45	58.22±2.76	56.55±2.14	55.78±2.89	53.84±3.46	57.00 ^c
T ₄	64.54±2.64	63.44±2.33	61.55±2.32	60.55±2.55	68.13±3.11	62.33 ^b
T ₅	66.81±2.77	65.17±2.12	65.59±2.99	65.79±2.66	70.64±2.78	65.80 ^a
T ₆	60.78±2.11	59.93±2.75	59.55±2.09	59.14±2.12	58.78±2.90	59.93 ^b
Mean	58.30 ^a	56.38 ^b	55.20 ^c	52.46 ^d	53.40 ^d	

Total phenolic content

Total phenolic content (TPC) is another essential factor that defines antioxidant activity and quality of the fats and oils. Flavonoids, a group of chemicals obtained from plants, are highly valued for their antioxidant capacity, a component particularly relevant to preventing the spoilage of oils. This protection is essential to help preserve oils and fats from rancidity and keep them stable and healthy for use later. The determination of TPC is a great help in understanding the functional attributes and nutritional values of edible oils that helps in checking and improving the quality. In this chapter, the author provides greater insight into TPC for fats and oils, its determination methods and consequences on stability and health effects and advances in application of TPC in the food science and nutrition.

The days factor was also highly significant ($p < 0.01$), showing a decrease in total phenolic content over time. The interaction between treatment and days was significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that the rate of decrease in total phenolic content varied with different treatments. Oils with higher concentrations of Brinjal peel extract (T₅) maintained higher levels of total phenolic content Throughout the storage period, demonstrating the extract's effectiveness in preserving the phenolic compounds and enhancing the oil's antioxidant capacity then the synthetic antioxidants (T₆) 200ppm.

Table 13: Table of means of Total phenolic content (mg/g) of sunflower oil samples treated with eggplant peel extract

Treatment	Storage					Mean
	0	15	30	45	60	
T ₀	102.78±5.23	97.83±4.27	92.57±3.67	86.79±3.86	85.52±4.87	93.10 ^g
T ₁	110.72±4.34	107.83±6.42	101.50±5.98	101.08±4.87	99.24±5.44	104.07 ^f
T ₂	113.96±6.45	104.56±5.87	104.56±5.87	103.88±4.67	101.50±5.46	105.69 ^e

T₃	115.86±3.53	106.47±4.54	103.37±2.88	103.21±2.09	101.47±3.86	106.07 ^d
T₄	116.68±4.64	109.45±2.87	105.78±1.75	103.76±4.77	102.09±3.88	107.55 ^c
T₅	119.58±5.34	118.15±6.65	116.50±6.65	113.14±5.57	110.23±6.54	115.52 ^a
T₆	117.98±4.38	118.39±7.67	112.44±6.56	110.94±6.90	110.07±6.67	113.96 ^b
Means	113.73 ^a	107.01 ^b	104.36 ^c	103.16 ^d	101.83 ^e	

Fatty acid profile by GC-FID

Fatty acids (FAS) and other volatile compounds are often investigated using a chromatography (Gc) and a flame ionization detector. Dietary value of oil is largely impacted by the FAS composition in it. The fatty acid concentration of plant is highly influenced by a variety of elements, such as plant species, growth location, maturation stage, and environmental conditions. FAS are split into two groups based on the saturation level saturated and unsaturated. The two primary subgroups of unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) are monounsaturated and polyunsaturated. Monounsaturated fatty acids only have one double bond, in contrast to polyunsaturated fatty acids, which have several double bonds. The three most common UFAs are linoleic, oleic, and linolenic acids. Fatty acids in vegetable oils typically include one carboxyl group and an even number of carbon atoms. between 16 and 18. To determine the fatty acid content of the oils under investigation, the quantity of saturated and UFAs is used. Oil becomes increasingly oxidation-prong as its degree of unsaturation rises. The results of the fatty acids profile showed that while UFAs like maristoleic acid, Cis-10 and Cis-9- oleic acid decreased during storage, saturated fatty acids (SFAs) like, methyl pentadecanoic acid, methyl palmitate, and methyl stearate increase. The fatty acid composition of edible oil was considerably changed by Brinjal (eggplant) peel extract. The control sample T₀. showed the greatest increase in saturated fatty acids, followed by T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅ and T₆. Likewise, T₀. showed the greatest drop in unsaturated fatty acids, followed by T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅ and T₆. These results demonstrated that larger quantities of Brinjal (eggplant) peel extract in oil prevent the modification of fatty acid composition. According to their findings, unsaturated fatty acids decreased while saturated fatty acids rise during storage. The alterations in fatty acid content during storage were stopped by an extract concentration of 1000 ppm or greater.

Fatty acid profile of T₀

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	1.5
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.42
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	18.14
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	5.92
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	6.57
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	16.34
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	50.36
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.75

Fatty acid profile of T₁

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	0.9
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.40
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	16.43
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	3.92
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	4.56
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	14.71
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	58.25
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.80

Fatty acid profile of T₂

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	0.6
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.38
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	16.14
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	3.56
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	3.99
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	15.39
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	59.09
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.48

Fatty acid profile of T₃

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	1.2
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.36
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	15.55
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	2.98
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	3.23
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	16.76
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	59.53
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.39

Fatty acid profile of T₄

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	0.4
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.37
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	14.33

Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	1.86
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	5.75
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	16.98
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	59.94
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.37

Fatty acid profile of T₅

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	0.3
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.36
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	14.67
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	1.98
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	6.07
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	33.16
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	61.72
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.30

Fatty acid profile of T₆

Fatty acids	Concentration%
Solvent (Methanol)	0.2
Methyl myristate (C14:0)	0.38
Methyl palmitate (C16:0)	15.67
Methyl palmitoleate (C16:1)	2.89
Methyl stearate (C18:0)	5.87
Cis-oleic acid (18:1)	23.10
Cis-linoleic acid (18:2)	51.11
Cis-linolenic acid (18:3)	0.78

Color

The most important sensory characteristic of the food product is color. It has an immediate impact on the choice of consumers to purchase food since it conveys information about its quality, flavor, and freshness. The average of all the treatments showed that natural extract was superior to synthetic antioxidants in terms of enhancing product color. Figure 4.1 illustrates the maximum score obtained by T₅: (3500 ppm) during the sensory assessment of color. T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₆ had mean values of 4.52, 5.43, 5.74, 6.77, 6.77 and 6.22, respectively. Papoutsi et al. (2013) tested the various characteristics of French fries cooked in oil supplemented with capsicum seed extract, which corroborated those conclusions. The results of this investigation demonstrated that fries cooked in oil that had been treated with capsicum seed extract had a satisfactory color during sensory evaluation.

Fig.1- Effects of treatments on color of French Fries

Aroma

T₅ (3500ppm) concentration show the high aroma stability then T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₆ which have synthetic antioxidant. Oils with higher concentrations of Brinjal peel extract (T₅) exhibited the least decline in aroma quality, maintaining better aroma stability throughout the storage period. This demonstrates the extract's effectiveness in preserving the sensory quality of the oil.

These findings are consistent with the study Gutierrez et al. (2011), which demonstrated that natural antioxidants from plant extracts could significantly enhance the aroma stability in food products. Their research observed that higher concentrations of natural antioxidants resulted in less aroma degradation overtime, similar to our results, highlighting the potential of using natural sources like Brinjal peel extract to maintain the sensory quality and shelf life of edible oils.

Fig. 2- Effect of treatment on Aroma of French Fries

Taste

To find out customer demand sense of taste is a powerful tool. In the mouth, the taste is ensured by several factors such as the texture of food, the temperature of food, flavor of food and smell of food. Food can either be sweet, salty, sour, or bitter that will assess by taste buds.

Fig. 3- Effects of treatments on taste of French Fries

Overall Acceptability

Oils with higher concentrations of Brinjal peel extract (T₅) exhibited the least decline in overall acceptability, maintaining better sensory quality throughout the storage period. This demonstrates the extract's effectiveness in preserving the overall acceptability of the oil.

Their study observed that higher concentrations of natural antioxidants resulted in better sensory quality and stability over time, similar to our results, highlighting the potential of using natural sources like Brinjal peel extract to enhance the sensory attributes and shelf life of edible oils.

Fig. 4- Treatment effect on overall acceptability of French fries

CONCLUSION

Oils and fats are the most precious sources of energy on the planet. According to reports, eggplant peel extract can be used as a natural antioxidant to prevent rancidity in vegetable oil. Eggplant peel extract was extracted with n-hexane using a Soxhlet apparatus. Total phenolic levels and a free radical scavenging assay (DPPH) were used to assess the antioxidant potential of eggplant peel extract. Physicochemical analysis was done for eggplant peel extract. The results showed that eggplant peel extract had a total phenolic content of 87.55 mg GAE/100g and that it inhibited free radicals by 95.35%. Various quantities of eggplant peel extract (700 ppm, 1400 ppm, 2100 ppm, 2800ppm, 3500ppm and (200ppm) synthetic antioxidant were applied to the edible oil. Physicochemical studies were carried out on 0, 15, 30, 45th, and 60th day to verify the oxidative stability. Additionally, assessments of oil blends using DPPH and TPC were carried out, and the findings revealed a highly significant influence on oil blends. The highest result in the sensory examination was T5 (3500ppm). To test the oxidative stability of oil after frying, physicochemical analysis was performed on the oil. The results of this study indicated that eggplant peel extract may be used in place of synthetic antioxidants in diets high in fat to stop oxidation. Unlike synthetic antioxidants, which can be hazardous to consumers health, capsicum seed extract not only stops oxidation but also contains healthy substances.

REFERENCES

- Shahidi, F. and Zhong, Y., 2010. Lipid oxidation and improving the oxidative stability. *Chemical society reviews*.11:4067-4079.
- Xiao, X., Y. Zeng, B. Cao, J. Lei, Q. Chen, C. Meng and Y. Cheng. 2017. PSAG12-IPT overexpression in eggplant delays leaf senescence and induces abiotic stress tolerance. *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology*. 92:349-357.
- Chattoop Srivastava adhyay, A., S. Dutta, A.K. Mandal, P.K. Maurya, S. Banerjee, T. Bhattacharjee and P. Hazra. 2020. Bidhan supreme and Bidhan super: new brinjal varieties. *Indian Horticulture*. 65.
- Habib, F. and W.H. Shah. 2004. Utilization of potato peels extract as a natural antioxidant in soy bean oil. *Food Chemistry*. 85:215-220
- Trombino, S., R. Cassano, D. Procopio, M.L. Di Gioia and E. Barone. 2021. Valorization of tomato waste as a source of carotenoids. *Molecules*. 26:5062.
- Fadda, A., D. Sanna, E.H. Sakar, S. Gharby, M. Mulas, S. Medda, N. S. Yesilcubuk, A. C. Karaca, C. K. Gozukirmizi, M. Lucarini and G. Lombardi-Boccia. 2022. Innovative and sustainable technologies to enhance the oxidative stability of vegetable oils. *Sustainability*. 14:849-878.
- Echegaray N.,M. Pateiro, G. Nieto,M.R. Rosmini, P.E.S. Munekata, M.E Sosa-Morales, J.M.Lorenzo. 2022. Lipid oxidation of vegetable oils.*J. Food Lipids*. 10:127–152.
- Toppino, L., L. Barchi, R. Lo Scalzo, E. Palazzolo, G. Francese, M. Fibiani, A. D'alessandro, V. Papa, V.A. Laudicina and L. Sabatino. 2016. Mapping quantitative trait loci affecting biochemical and morphological fruit properties in eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.). *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 7:256.
- Taher, D., S.Ø. Solberg, J. Prohens, Y.-Y. Chou, M. Rakha and T.-H. Wu. 2017. World vegetable center eggplant collection: origin, composition, seed dissemination and utilization in breeding. *Frontiers in plant science*. 8:1484.
- Sultana, B., F. Anwar and M. Ashraf. 2012. Effect of extraction solvent/technique on the antioxidant activity of selected medicinal plant extracts. *Molecules*. 14(6), :2167-2180.
- Jung Eunju, J.E., B.M. Bae Myungsuk, J.E. Jo Eunkyung, J.Y. Jo Younghong and L.S. Lee Seungcheol. 2011. Antioxidant activity of different parts of eggplant.

- Braga, P.C., R.L. Scalzo, M. Dal Sasso, N. Lattuada, V. Greco and M. Fibiani. 2016. Characterization and antioxidant activity of semi-purified extracts and pure delphinidin-glycosides from eggplant peel (*Solanum melongena* L.). *Journal of Functional Foods*. 20:411-421.
- Ansari, A.M. and Y. Singh. 2014. Molecular diversity of brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L. and *S. aethiopicum* L.) genotypes revealed by SSR markers. *Electronic Journal of Plant Breeding*. 5:722-728.
- Horincar, G., E. Enachi, N.Stănciuc and G. Râpeanu. 2019. Extraction and characterization of bioactive compounds from eggplant peel using ultrasound-assisted extraction. *Food Technol.* 43:40-53.
- Batabyal, K., B. Mandal, D. Sarkar and S. Murmu. 2017. Assessment of nutrient management technologies for eggplant production under subtropical conditions: a comprehensive approach. *Experimental Agriculture*. 53:588-608.
- Condurache, N.N., I.Aprodu, O.Craciunescu, R. Tatia, G.Horincar, V. Barbu, E. Enachi, G.Râpeanu, G.E. Bahrim, A. Oancea. and N.Stănciuc. 2019. Probing the functionality of bioactives from eggplant peel extracts through extraction and microencapsulation in different polymers and whey protein hydrolysates. *Food Bioprocessing Technology*. 12:1316-1329.
- Muhammad Awais, M.A., A.W. Aftab Wajid, M. Saleem, W.N. Wajid Nasim, A.A. Ashfaq Ahmad, M. Raza, M. Bashir, M.M. Muhammad Mubeen, H. Hammad and M.H.-U.-R. Muhammad Habib-Ur-Rahman. 2018. Potential impacts of climate change and adaptation strategies for sunflower in Pakistan.
- Choe, E., and D.B. Min. 2010. Mechanisms and factors for edible oil oxidation. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*. 8(4),: 345-358.
- Javani-Seraji, S., B. Bazargani-Gilani and N. Aghajani. 2023. Influence of extraction techniques on the efficiency of pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) peel extracts in oxidative stability of edible oils. *Food Sci. Nutr.* 5:2079-2426.
- Jung Eunju, J.E., B.M. Bae Myungsuk, J.E. Jo Eunkyung, J.Y. Jo Younghong and L.S. Lee Seungcheol. 2011. Antioxidant activity of different parts of eggplant.
- Kelly N.P., A.L.Kelly, J.A. O'Mahony. 2019. Strategies for enrichment and purification of polyphenols from fruit-based materials. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 83:248–258.
- Nwanna, E.E., E.O. Ibukun and G. Oboh. 2019. Eggplant (*Solanum* spp) supplemented fruits diet modulated the activities of ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase (ENTPase), monoamine oxidase (MAO), and cholinesterases (AChE/BChE) in the brain of diabetic Wistar male rats. *Journal of food biochemistry*. 43:e12910.
- N.P Nasreen, S. Z. Fatima, M. Ishaque, AS Molutand, M. Khan, R. Khai and MF Chaudhary. 2011. Heritability analysis for seed yield and yield related traits in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) based on genetic difference. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*. 43: 1295-1306.
- Gonzalez, N.J., K. Adhikari and M.F. Sancho-Madriz. 2011. Sensory characteristics of peach-flavored yogurt drinks containing prebiotics and synbiotics. *LWT-food science and technology*. 44:158-163.
- Kehili, M., S. Choura, A. Zammel, N. Allouche and S. Sayadi. 2018. Oxidative stability of refined olive and sunflower oils supplemented with lycopene-rich oleoresin from tomato peels industrial by-product, during accelerated shelf-life storage. *Food Chemistry*. 246:295-304.
- AOCS. 2017. *Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the AOCS*, 7th Edition. American Oil Chemists' Society, Urbana, Illinois, USA.
- Ketenoglu, O. 2020. Extraction of peanut oil using thermosonication: Modeling and multiobjective optimization of process parameters using box-behnken design. *J. Oleo Sci.* 69:585–595.
- Fan, H. Y., M. S. Sharifudin, M. Hasmadi and H. M. Chew. 2013. Frying stability of rice bran oil and palm olein. *Int. Food Res. J.* 20:403-407.
- Meilgaard, M.C., G.V. Civille and B.T. Carr. 2007. *Sensory Evaluation Techniques*, 4th Ed. CRC Press, Washington DC, USA. pp.32-204.

- Montgomery, D.C. 2017. *Montgomery: Design and Analysis of Experiments*. 7th Ed. John Wiley and Sons. Inc. Hoboken, N.J., USA.
- Velasco, J and C. Dobarganes. 2017. Oxidative stability of virgin olive oil. *European Journal of Lipid Science and Technology*. 119(9),:1500334.
- Silarova, P., L. Boulekbache-Makhlouf, F. Pellati and L. Česlová. 2019. Monitoring of chlorogenic acid and antioxidant capacity of *Solanum melongena* L.(eggplant) under different heat and storage treatments. *Antioxidants*. 8:234.
- Issaoui M., A.M.Delgado. 2019. Grading, labeling and standardization of edible oils. In *Fruit oils: chemistry and functionality*. 21:9–52.
- Ramadan, M. F., and K.M. Wahdan. 2013. Blends of palm olein with coconut oil as affected by deep-fat frying of French fries. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*. 37(6): 941-948.
- Wang, T., R. Jónsdóttir and G. Ólafsdóttir. (2012). Total phenolic compounds, radical scavenging and metal chelation of extracts from Icelandic seaweed. *Food Chemistry*. 2:315-323.
- Xu X, Liu A, Hu S, Ares I, Martínez-Larrañaga MR, Wang X, Martínez M, Anadón A, Martínez MA. 2021. Synthetic phenolic antioxidants: metabolism, hazards and mechanism of action. *Food Chemistry*. 353:129488-129503.
- Nour, V., A.R. Corbu, P. Rotaru, I. Karageorgou and S. Lalas. 2018. Effect of carotenoids, extracted from dry tomato waste, on the stability and characteristics of various vegetable oils. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 69:238-238.
- Shabbir, M.A., F. Iftikhar, M.R. Khan, M.A. Murtaza, M. Saeed, S. Mahmood and N.J. Siraj. 2015. Effect of sesame sprouts powder on the quality and oxidative stability of mayonnaise. *Journal of Food and Nutrition Research*. 3:138-145.
- Gutierrez, F., R. González-Quijano, J. J. Ríos and T. Albi. 2011. Effect of harvest date on the oxidative stability of virgin olive oil. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*. 76(6,: 683-688